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New records of the tephritid and picture-winged flies (Diptera: Tephritidae, Ulidiidae) from Chernivtsi Region (Ukraine). I. Floristic hotspots as refugia for flies

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Korneyev, S. V., Babytskiy, A. I., Kameneva E. P. & Korneyev, V. A. New records of the tephritid and picture-winged flies (Diptera: Tephritidae, Ulidiidae) from Chernivtsi Region (Ukraine). I. Floristic hotspots as refugia for flies. — Thirty-nine species of Tephritidae and four species of Ulidiidae are recorded for the first time from Chernivetska Region of Ukraine, which remained a “white spot” on the map of distribution of many Diptera groups. This diversity was found on two botanical preserves with rich flora represented by both meadow and steppe vegetation. A numerous population of endangered species *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld 1867 is found.

Key words: Ukraine, Diptera, Tephritidae, Ulidiidae, protected species, Chernivetska Region, new records.

Корнєєв С. В., Бабицький А. І., Каменєва Є. П., Корнєєв В. А. Нові знахідки осетницевих і стрічкокрилкових мух (Diptera: Tephritidae, Ulidiidae) з Чернівецької області (Україна). I. Флористичні «гарячі точки» як рефугіуми для мух. З Чернівецької області України, яка залишилася «білою плямою» на карті поширення багатьох груп двокрилих, вперше зареєстровано 39 видів Tephritidae та 4 види Ulidiidae. Таке різноманіття виявлено у двох ботанічних заказниках[з багатою флорою, представленою як лучною, так і степовою рослинністю. Знайдено численну популяцію зникаючого виду *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld 1867.

Ключові слова: Україна, двокрили, Tephritidae, Ulidiidae, види, що охороняються, Чернівецька область, нові знахідки.

Introduction

The true fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) and the related families of the picture-winged (Ulidiidae), signal (Platystomatidae) and scarab flies (Pyrgotidae) are among the most spectacular dipteran insects due to their appearance of patterned bodies and wings, mating behaviour and high diversity worldwide and especially in the tropics and subtropics. Many species of Tephritidae are noxious pests of fruits and vegetables, but some of them also control weeds as seed feeders and thus are in the focus of studies, but the “satellite” families, which are represented predominantly

by the species with saprophagous larvae, remain poorly examined.

In the last four decades, only a few papers considered the tephritoid flies of Ukraine or its different regions (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985, 1987; Korneyev & Kameneva, 1987; Korneyev, 1987, 2003; Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Korneyev, 2013; Korneyev & Konovalov, 2010; Korneyev & Klasa, 2016; Kameneva & Greve Jensen, 2013; Kameneva et al., 2020; Verves et al., 1984, 1989, 1993; Volkov et al. 1984).

Currently, the numbers of recorded species, including unconfirmed but reliable species is 146 for Tephritidae (Korneyev & Klasa, 2016; UkrBIN, 2021), 37 for Ulidiidae

dae, 5 for Platystomatidae and 1 for Pyrgotidae (Kameneva et al., 2020).

Only one species, *Tephritis formosa* was known in collections from Chernivtsi Region of Ukraine (Kameneva, Korneyev, 1985; Korneyev & Klasa, 2016), which remained a white spot on the map of Ukrainian Tephritoidea.

In 2019 and 2021, through the kindness of Dmytro Yakushenko, Alla Tokaryuk and Illia Chorney, the authors took five collecting trips to two areas in Bukovinian Precarpathia having extraordinary diversity of meadow tall herb-dominated vegetation rich in steppe elements in Chernivtsi Region: the “Malyovanka” Botanical Preserve (Okruh hill) and “Dzyurkach” area near Spaska, both located close to Chernivtsi city boundaries. Plant assemblages were composed of forest species, dry grassland species, and also species of transitional habitats, i.e. heliophilous and semi-shade species, which are not adapted to very dry soils (Roleček et al., 2021).

Descriptions of the “Malyovanka” Botanical Preserve (slopes of Okruh hill) were provided by Tokaryuk et al. (2018); additional information on the vegetation of “Dzyurkach” / Spaska locality was provided also by Roleček et al. (2014).

“Dzyurkach” area was found to have natural stands of *Echinops exaltatus*, the host plant of a recently rediscovered tephritid fly *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld, 1867, a rare species known only from its type series for 150 years and included on the Red Data List of Ukraine as possibly extinct (Korneyev, 2009). Recently, few small populations of *E. exaltatus* infested by *U. dzieduszyckii* were rediscovered in the valleys of northern tributaries of Dnister — Dzhuryn and Zbruch (Korneyev et al., 2016 and unpublished data). On the contrary, the stands of *E. exaltatus* in “Dzyurkach” locality were estimated to contain 300 to 500 separate plants. Trying to find out if these plants are also infested by *Urophora dzieduszyckii*, we visited the stands 5 times, but only in the latest two visits numerous adult flies of that species were observed on the plants. As a by-side result of these observations, numerous species of

Tephritidae and Ulidiidae were collected for the first time from Chernivtsi Region.

Material and Methods

Material was collected predominantly in the two localities, in the area c. 300–600 m in radius of:

“Spaska” = Dzyurkach locality near Spaska village (Fig. 1), 48.3017°N, 25.7759°E;

“Zavoloka” = Okruh hill slopes near Zavoloka, Malyovanka Botanical Preserve (Fig. 2), 48.2522°N, 25.8905°E.

Some casual collectings were made in Khotyn Historical fortress — 48.5209°N, 26.4992°E and vicinity of Valiava village (“Valava”) — 48.4748°N, 25.8701°E.

Flies were collected either by sweeping net, then picked by aspirator (or directly into the aspirator from host plants to prevent destruction of protected and rare plants) and anesthetized then with acetic ether or in a fridge.

All the material is deposited in the collection of I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, Kyiv (SIZK).

Family Tephritidae — True Fruit Flies

Acanthiophilus helianthi (Rossi, 1794)

Material examined. Khotyn, 21.06.2021, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Spaska, 24.07.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 05.09.2019, 1 ♀, 10.07.2021, 2 ♂, 2 ♀, 23.07.2021, 3 ♂, 4 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Valava, 23.06.2021, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 3 ♂, 7 ♀, 23.07.2021, 2 ♂, 4 ♀, 23.07.2021, 2 ♂, 5 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Central and Southern Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Wide oligophagous species; larvae in flower heads of various species of *Centaurea*, as well as some *Carduus* and *Galactites* (Merz, 1994); in Chernivtsi Re-

Figs 1–2. Collecting sites: 1 — Spaska.; 2 — Zavoloka.

gion associated with *Centaurea scabiosa* and *C. jacea*. Overwinters as adults.

Acinia corniculata (Zetterstedt, 1819)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Great Britain and France to Finland and Ukraine (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). In western and central Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Strictly oligophagous or monophagous species; on the meadows; larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea jacea* (Merz, 1994). Overwinters as larvae in cocoons on the ground.

Aciura coryli (Rossi, 1794)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Southern Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). In southern Ukraine and Dnister basin; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. In the steppes; larvae in flowers of *Phlomis* and *Ballota* (Lamiaceae) (Merz, 1994).

Campiglossa bidentis (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Dioxya bidentis (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830): Merz & Korneyev, 2004.

Material examined. Spaska, 05.09.2019, 6 ♂, 3 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.), 22.06.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Very common throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. In meadows and wetlands; larvae in flower heads of *Bidens cernua* and *B. tripartita*; reported also from *Galinsoga*, *Tagetes erecta* and other introduced Heliantheae garden plants (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Campiglossa producta (Loew, 1844)

Material examined. Spaska, 05.09.2019, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Central and Southern Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Crepis*, *Leontodon*, *Chondrilla*, *Sonchus* and some other Cichorieae plants (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Carpomya schineri (Loew, 1856)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Central and Southern Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Southern Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in fruits of various *Rosa* (Rosaceae) (Merz, 1994).

Chaetorellia jaceae (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 7 ♂, 3 ♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 22.06.2021, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 10.07.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 2 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 09.07.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 23.07.2021, 3 ♂, 2 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea jacea* and *C. nigra* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Chaetorellia loricata (Rondani, 1870)

Material examined. Spaska, 23.07.2021, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Central and southern Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine, sporadically; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa*, *C. alpestris* and *C. tenuifolia* (Asteraceae); overwinters as larvae in flower head or rarely as adults (Merz, 1994).

Chaetostomella cylindrica (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 1 ♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 2 ♂, 23.07.2021, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). All Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea*, *Cirsium*, *Carduus*, *Serratula* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994), which possibly form different host races or cryptic species.

Dithryca guttularis (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1 ♂ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Northern and Central Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Transcarpathia, Ternopil, Cherkasy; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae induce galls on rhizome of *Achillea* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Ensina sonchi (Linnaeus, 1767)

Material examined. Spaska, 05.09.2019, 2 ♂, 3 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.), 22.06.2021, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1 ♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe, except Iceland and North (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Crepis*, *Lactuca*, *Leontodon*, *Picris*, *Sonchus*, *Tragopogon*, *Chondrilla* and some other Cichorieae plants (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Euleia heraclei (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Spaska, 05.09.2019, 1 ♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Northern and Central Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae mine leaves of *Angelica* and many other genera of Apiaceae (Merz, 1994).

Myopites inulae (Roser, 1840)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 10♂, 7♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Germany and Austria to Iran and Kazakhstan (V. Korneyev, unpublished data). Throughout Ukraine: Ternopil, Kyiv, Crimea; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae induce galls in flower heads of *Imula salicina* (= *Pentanema saicinum*) (Asteraceae) (V. Korneyev, unpublished data).

Orellia falcata (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. Spaska, 22.06.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 10.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 23.07.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe to the Near East and Central Asia (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in stems of *Tragopogon* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994). Overwinters as larvae in lower part of stems.

Tephritis bardanae (Schrank, 1803)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂, 23.07.2021, 2♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe and Palearctic Asia (introduced to Sakhalin) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Arctium* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994). Overwinters as adults.

Tephritis crepidis Hendel, 1927

Material examined. Spaska, 22.06.2021, 4♂ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 10.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Europe, from Pyrenees to Carpathians (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Ivano-Frankivsk (Hoverla) (Korneyev & Klasa, 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Crepis biennis* and *C. pyrenaica* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Tephritis dioscurea (Loew, 1856)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe, sporadically (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Zakarpatska to Sumy and

Crimea, sporadically (Korneyev & Klasa, 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Crepis biennis* and *C. pyrenaica* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Tephritis formosa (Loew, 1844)

Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985; Korneyev, 2016.

Material examined. Stavchany [48.51°N, 25.68°E], 25.07.1959, 1♂ (collector unknown).

Distribution. Central and Southern Europe, North Africa, Near East, Caucasus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Chernivtsi & Crimea (Korneyev, 2016).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Sonchus asper* and *S. oleraceus* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Tephritis hurvitzii Freidberg, 1981

Korneyev et al., 2021.

Material examined. Spaska, 23.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Central Asia, Near East, Asia Minor, Greece, Cyprus (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Crimea (Korneyev, 2003), Donetsk, Zaporizhzhya (Korneyev et al., 2021); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. In Israel, larvae in gregarious stem galls just below flower heads of *Tragopogon longirostris* and *Scorzonera syriaca* (Asteraceae) (Freidberg & Kugler, 1989). Known previously only from Crimea, it was simultaneously collected in the three distant localities of mainland Ukraine. See Korneyev et al. (2021) for distribution, host plant and biology details.

Tephritis neesii (Meigen, 1830)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 1♀ (S. Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 22.06.2021, 3♂, 2♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 23.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 2♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv (Korneyev, 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Leontodon vulgaris* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Tephritis postica (Loew, 1844)

Material examined. Khotyn, 21.06.2021, 1♂ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Southern and Central Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Korneyev & Korneyev, 2018). Ukraine: Crimea (Korneyev, 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record from continental Ukraine**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Onopordum acanthium* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Tephritis separata Rondani, 1871

Material examined. Stavchany [48.51°N, 25.68°E], 25.07.1959, 1♂ (I. Akimov); Spaska, 24.07.2019, 1♂, 2♀ (S. Korneyev, V. Korneyev

& Babytskiy leg.), 10.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 3♂, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Ternopil, Mykolaiv, Kharkiv, Donetsk (Korneyev, 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Picris hieracioides* and *P. rigida* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994; Korneyev, 2016).

Tephritis valida (Loew, 1858) (Figs 3–4)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂, 2♀, 23.07.2021, 6♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Romania, Moldova, Caucasus, Northern Iran (Merz & Korneyev, 2004; Korneyev, 2016). Ukraine: Ternopil (Korneyev et al., 2016); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Inula helenium* (Asteraceae) (Korneyev et al., 2016).

Terellia ceratocera (Hendel, 1913)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe, except South (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv, Cherkasy (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Cirsium eriophorum* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994); in Kyiv, in flower heads of *C. decussatum*. The flies were collected on flower heads of *Echinops exaltatus*, which cannot be its host plant, but no *C. decussatum* have been detected in this area, so this needs further identification of the species.

Terellia colon (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 3♂, 1♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); 23.07.2021, 2♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 6♂, 3♀, 23.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv, Cherkasy (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Terellia plagiata (Dahlbom, 1850)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 09.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe, except South (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv, Cherkasy (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Figs 3–4 *Tephritis valida*: 3 — male on young flower head; 4 — *Inula helenium*, its host plant.

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa* and *C. alpestris* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994).

Terellia cf. longicauda (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 11♂, 3♀ (S Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe, sporadically (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in stems of *Centaurea scabiosa* and *C. alpestris* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994). The second instar larvae migrate into stems from flower heads.

Terellia pseudovirens (Hering, 1940)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 9♂, 3♀, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Eastern Mediterranean region, Middle East (Zarghani et al., 2016); south of European Russia, western Qazaqstan. Ukraine: Kherson, Donetsk (Kameneva & Korneyev, 1985); Odesa, Luhansk (V. Korneyev, unpublished data); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae flower heads of *Serratula xeranthemoides*, *S. radiata* and *S. spp.* (Fig. 5.) (Asteraceae) (Korneyev, 1982; Zarghani et al., 2016).

Fig. 5. *Serratula* sp.: host plant of *Terellia pseudovirens*.

Terellia ruficauda (Fabricius, 1794) [black morph] (Fig. 6)

Material examined. Spaska, 24.07.2019, 7♂, 6♀ (S. Korneyev, V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Spaska, 10.07.2021, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 7♂, 6♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 4♂, 23.07.2021, 2♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Central and northern Europe (S. Korneyev, unpublished data); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. In flower heads of *Cirsium palustre*, *C. canum* and *C. oleraceum* (S. Korneyev, unpublished data). Status of this “colour morph” is still disputable. It may belong to a separate species.

Terellia tussilaginis (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. Spaska, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe and Palaearctic Asia (introduced to Sakhalin) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Throughout Ukraine; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in seeds of *Arctium* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994). Overwinters as larvae.

Terellia winthemi (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Spaska, 23.07.2021, 7♂, 2♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy, Kharkiv (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Fig. 6. *Terellia ruficauda*: on *Cirsium oleraceum*, Spaska..

Fig. 7. *Carduus* sp., host plant of *Terellia winthemi*, Spaska..

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of *Carduus crispus* and *C. defloratus* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994) (Fig. 7). Overwinters as larvae.

Trupanea stellata (Fuesslin, 1775)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Palaearctic Region (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: widespread (Korneyev & Kameneva, 1985); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Larvae in flower heads of various Asteraceae (Merz, 1994).

Urophora affinis Frauenfeld, 1857

Material examined. Spaska, 22.06.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 1♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe except North (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Kyiv; Cherkasy, Odesa, Kherson, Donetsk, Luhansk, Crimea (Korneyev & White, 1996); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces single galls in flower heads of *Centaurea stoebe* and *C. diffusa* (Asteraceae) (Merz, 1994, as *C. maculosa*). Overwinters as larvae.

Urophora cuspidata (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Spaska, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 2♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Khmelnytsky, Kharkiv, Crimea (Korneyev & White, 1996); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa* (Asteraceae) (Korneyev & White, 1996). Overwinters as larvae.

Urophora dzieduszyckii Frauenfeld, 1867

Korneyev, 2009; Korneyev et al., 2016, 2019.

Material examined. Spaska, 10.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 2♂ (V. Korneyev leg., dead specimens in spider or sweeping net).

Distribution. Ukraine, Turkey, Syria, Israel (Korneyev et al., 2019). Ternopil (Korneyev et al., 2016, 2019); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. In flower heads of *Echinops exaltatus* (Asteraceae) (Korneyev et al., 2016, 2019). Overwinters as larvae. In July 2021, observations in the stand of *E. exaltatus* in Spaska, revealed up to 30 mating couples in one day; the local population is estimated to have up to 1.5 thousand of individuals in 300–500 plants. This is the largest known population of this protected species in Europe. More precise estimation needs special methods of recording without extraction of flies from the nature. Protection status of Dzhurchyn locality needs reconsideration.

Urophora jaceana (Hering, 1935)

Material examined. Spaska, 10.07.2021, 3♂, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 2♂ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: widespread (Korneyev & White, 1996); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Centaurea jaceae* (Asteraceae) (Korneyev & White, 1996). Overwinters as larvae.

Urophora lopholomae White & Korneyev, 1989

Material examined. Valava, 23.06.2021, 1♂ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 3♂, 3♀, 23.07.2021, 11♂, 6♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: Khmelnytsky, Kharkiv, Crimea (Korneyev & White, 1996); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Centaurea scabiosa* (Asteraceae) (White & Korneyev, 1989). Overwinters as larvae.

Urophora quadrifasciata (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Spaska, 22.06.2021, 2♂, 2♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.), 10.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 1♂ (V. Korneyev leg.); Zavoloka, 22.06.2021, 2♀ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev & Babytskiy leg.); Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 1♂, 23.07.2021, 1♂ (alcohol) (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: widespread; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Centaurea* spp. (Asteraceae) (Korneyev & White, 1996). Overwinters as larvae.

Urophora stylata (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Europe, Near East and Central Asia (Korneyev & White, 1996). Ukraine: widespread (Korneyev & White, 1996); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Cirsium arvense* and *Cirsium vulgare* (Asteraceae) (Korneyev & White, 1996). Overwinters as larvae.

Xyphosia miliaria (Schrank, 1781)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Throughout Palaearctic Region (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Ukraine: widespread; Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Notes. Induces galls in flower heads of *Cirsium* spp. and *Carduus* spp. (Asteraceae) (Merz & Korneyev, 2004). Overwinters as larvae.

Figs 8–11: female (8) and males (9–11) of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* on young flower heads of its host, *Echinops exaltatus*, Spaska.

Family Ulidiidae — Picture-Winged Flies

Herina paludum (Fallén, 1820)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 1♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 2♂, 4♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. West and Central Europe (Kameneva & Greve Jensen, 2013). Ukraine: Ternopil (Kameneva et al., 2020); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Herina palustris (Meigen, 1826)

Material examined. Zavoloka, 23.07.2021, 12♂, 11♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Most of Europe (Kameneva & Greve Jensen, 2013). Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil (Kameneva et al., 2020); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

Ulidia nigripennis Loew, 1845

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 3♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 2♂, 2♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. France to Ukraine (Kameneva & Greve Jensen, 2013). Ukraine: Kyiv, Ternopil, Kharkiv (Kameneva et al., 2020); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

***Ulidia parallela* Loew, 1845**

Material examined. Zavoloka, 09.07.2021, 6♂, 1♀, 23.07.2021, 1♀ (V. Korneyev leg.).

Distribution. Europe: Germany, Poland, Slovakia, Italy, Moldova, Bulgaria (Kameneva & Greve Jensen, 2013). Ukraine: Ternopil (Kameneva et al., 2020); Chernivtsi Region (**first record**).

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